

Arianism

also known as “Theology of Arius”

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Entry tags: Arianism, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Ancient Mediterranean, Arianism, Heresy

Arianism has been used as a term to designate theological beliefs attributed to Arius (c.250-336 CE), a Christian priest from Alexandria. Arius' written works survive only in fragments, making it difficult to reconstruct his beliefs. This is only complicated by countless attempts made by Arius' opponents to distort and ridicule his theological views. The most distinctive feature of Arianism is the relationship of the Son, Christ, to the Father, God. God, the Father, has absolute priority over all else, including the Son. According to Arius, the superiority of God, the Father, over Christ, the Son, was expressed by familial hierarchy according to which the Father was superior to the Son. Christ was begotten by God as a product of His will. Consequently, there was a time when Christ did not exist. As a creature of God, Christ cannot comprehend the nature of God, nor his own nature, but can lead others towards the worship of the one God. Arius' theological beliefs brought him into conflict with Alexander of Alexandria (250-326 or 328 CE), who supported the Origen's view of the eternal coexistence of the Father and the Son. Arius travelled to North Africa and the Near East and gained the support of other bishops, such as Eusebius of Caesarea and Eusebius of Nicomedia, who also believed that Alexander's stance jeopardized the unity of God and the primacy of the God-Father. The emperor Constantine summoned the Council of Nicaea in 325 CE and its debate generated the belief that Christ was coeternal and of the 'same substance' (ὁμοούσιος-homoousios, composed of ὁμός-homós, 'same' and οὐσία-ousía, 'substance') as God. This council consequently deemed Arius' beliefs as heretic and he, along with two bishops who refused to accept the outcome of the council, were sent into exile. Constantine's decision to invite bishops throughout the Empire to condemn Arius' beliefs helped to cement a precedent according to which imperial intervention could summon councils to maintain the unity of the Christian church, and by extension, the Roman Empire. However, the Council of Nicaea would not resolve the conflict over Arianism. Arius was recalled from exile by Emperor Constantine in 328, and invited to return to Alexandria, but prevented from reintegrating the community of the Egyptian Church by Athanasius, bishop of Alexandria (296 or 298-373 CE). Arius was reinstated in 335 and even accepted the tenets of Nicene creed when examined by Constantine at a council in Constantinople in early 336. Arius died in 336 before he could return to Alexandria. When Arius died, Constantine considered his beliefs orthodox. Sources from the late fourth and fifth centuries generated gruesome accounts of Arius' death. A bitter critic, Socrates Scholasticus, wrote that Arius shamefully died from an intestinal hemorrhage, a fitting punishment for his heretic views. The narratives that 'Arianism' was characterized by a coherent set of beliefs and that 'Arians' were a defined groups with shared beliefs and continuity over times are a fantasy. The term 'Arian' was never used by its adherents but was rather employed to slander the beliefs of individuals deemed heretics, who may not even have practiced any beliefs held by Arius himself. The Homoian beliefs of emperors Constantius II, Valens, the Goths (and later Ostrogoths, Visigoths) as well as Anomoeans (also called Eunomians) were stigmatized as heretics by their opponents through the label of 'Arian'. Arianism (and its associate theological doctrine, Homoianism) was once again condemned in the Edict of Thessalonica (27 February 380) and at the Council of Constantinople of 381, summoned by emperor Theodosius I. Nevertheless, at the turn of the fifth century, scholars believe that Homoian Christians would have composed a majority in Constantinople.

Date Range: 325 CE - 671 CE

Region: Arianism Map (Roman Empire)

Region tags: Europe, Western Europe

Arius lived in the Roman Empire. The (artificially) defined chronology of this entry begins with the Council of Nicaea in 325 CE and ends with the deposition of the last Lombard King, Garibald in 671, who held 'Arian' beliefs.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ayres, Lewis. *Nicaea and Its Legacy: An Approach to Fourth-Century Trinitarian Theology*. 1st ed. Oxford University Press: Oxford, 2004.
- Source 2: Hanson, Richard P. C. *The Search for the Christian Doctrine of God: The Arian Controversy 318-381*. Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 2006.
- Source 3: Simonetti, Manlio. *La crisi ariana nel IV secolo*. *Studia ephemeridis 'Augustinianum'*. Roma: Institutum patristicum Augustinianum, 1975.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.fourthcentury.com/documents-of-the-early-arian-controversy/>
- Source 1 Description: List of documents from early Arianism
- Source 2 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20221124111549/https://www.fourthcentury.com/conciliar-creeds-of-the-fourth-century/>
- Source 2 Description: List of Conciliar creeds and useful primary sources about each council
- Source 3 URL: <https://religiondatabase.org/browse/1653>
- Source 3 Description: Homoian Christianity amongst the Visigoths DRH Entry

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 671 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.newworldencyclopedia.org/entry/Arianism>

– Source 1 Description: Arianism entry

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/2816.htm>

– Source 1 Description: Athanasius, 'Orations against the Arians'

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.fourthcentury.com/urkunde-4b/>

– Source 1 Description: A letter by Athanasius written at the behest of Alexander of Alexandria rallying anti-Arian support (Henos somatos letter). From 319 CE.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.fourthcentury.com/urkunde-14/>

– Source 2 Description: A letter by Alexander of Alexandria warning Alexander of Byzantium about the 'Arian conspiracy' (He philarchos). From 324 CE.

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.fourthcentury.com/arius-thalia-intro/>

– Source 3 Description: Arius' Thalia

Notes: The Thalia survives in 'Orations Against the Arians' 1.5-6 and 'On the Councils of Arminum and Seleucia' 15.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.fourthcentury.com/urkunde-34/>

– Source 1 Description: Letter of Emperor Constantine to Arius (c.333 CE)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/2702.htm>

– Source 1 Description: Theodoret's 'Ecclesiastical History', esp. book 1.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.tertullian.org/fathers/philostorgius.htm>

– Source 2 Description: Philostorgius' 'Ecclesiastical History'

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 671 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The conflict between Arius and Alexander of Alexandria was important enough to garner the attention of Constantine and cause him to call the Council of Nicea in 325 CE.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Councils would establish whether a view was 'orthodox' or not. Arians were designated as such by their Christian opponents. So-called Arians would not have constituted a coherent group, as mentioned in the entry above.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: More generally, members of the clergy would try to attract converts to Christianity. Arianism should not be understood as a firm set of beliefs, but rather as the thoughts of an individual who attracted a following and support. During councils, Arius and his followers would have tried to persuade other clerics that their beliefs were orthodox and the correct reading of Scripture.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: From the conversion of Constantine in 312, Christian clerics and churches were given tax exemptions. Under the reigns of Constantine, Constantius II and Valens, Homoian Christianity, later called Arianism by its opponents, was declared orthodox. They would consequently have benefited from tax exemptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Old and New Testaments

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Arius' beliefs do not differ from Christianity in this regard.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Not in any way distinctive from Christianity in the 4th century CE. To my knowledge, scholarship has not identified an 'architecture of Arianism'.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: No, see above.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is iconography present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Same beliefs as Nicene Christianity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Inhumation, like in Christianity more generally.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Same as Christianity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: No difference from Christianity more generally in this time period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Same as Nicene Christianity, with the only difference being that Christ was created by God in the same manner as other creatures. The substance of the Father is similar not identical, to that of the Son.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Same as Nicene Christianity, although more emphasis on the supreme nature of the Father over the Son and Holy Spirit .

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: Although sources do portray Roman emperors as divinely chosen and central to the relationship between God and the Roman Empire.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: Although the cult of martyrs may have had much akin with the concept of 'previously human spirits'.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Such as angels and demons. Same as Nicene Christianity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Angels are positive and demons are negative.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Although there were angels and demons which could torment the living.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Notes: I am not aware of Arius' beliefs on divine providence, but fourth century Christianity more generally believed in divine intervention to protect or punish. Furthermore, the fact that practices

enacted in the earthly kingdom (e.g. baptism) would be necessary to reach the divine kingdom implies a sort of 'surveillance'.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Demons could represent obstacles, but not necessarily punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Same as above. God rewards those worthy with Paradise.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation of the all the dead, just and unjust during the Second Coming. The righteous vanquish the unjust and the world is then the kingdom of God. Whether this is superior, with regards to the last two questions, is up for debate.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Martyrs go straight to the divine kingdom without having to go to purgatory.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Although Jesus is neither coeternal nor of the same essence as God, he is nevertheless the messiah.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Same values and moral code as Christianity.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Can be recommended, but would not have been enforced.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Can be recommended, but would not have been enforced.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Attending Church, as a communal activity, would have been an integral part of what it meant to be a Christian.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Can be recommended, but would not have been enforced.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– I don't know

Notes: Perhaps, Arius' opponents seem to have conducted orthodoxy checks. In a letter addressed to Alexander of Alexandria and Arius, Constantine implies that Alexander had conducted orthodoxy checks by asking members of his clergy to write exegesis. This letter is contained within Eusebius' Life of Constantine 2.64-72

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Wine is drunk during the Eucharist, as a representation of drinking Christ's blood.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Arius and those with similar beliefs lived in the Roman Empire.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Grain was distributed through the annona but this has no link to Arius or his beliefs.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: As mentioned in the entry above, the idea that 'Arians' were a coherent group is a fantasy.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire, as evidenced of letters written by emperors to Arian and his circle, but also the Church, usually the infrastructure of the Nicene Christianity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the Roman Empire

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the Roman Empire.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the Roman Empire

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Supplied by the Roman Empire.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the Roman Empire.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Priscillian was executed in 385 CE.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the Roman Empire

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Goths, an important source of military recruits in the Late Roman Empire, were 'Arian' Homoian Christians. See entry on 'Homoian Christianity amongst Visigoths', DRH.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: While residing in the Roman Empire, those called Arians were protected by the Roman army.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latin and Greek.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Greek and Latin.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: I am not sure whether Arian and his followers' Christian calendar was in any way different from those of Nicene Christians.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 800 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Food Production

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some would have had access to the annona.

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